

FRAMEWORK FOR ASSET DIGITALIZATION: A HOLISTIC APPROACH FOR ENHANCED MANAGEMENT AND RELIABILITY IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract

Despite the notable technological advancements, especially in areas like digital twins, we are still confronted with a significant challenge in the process of asset digitization. This challenge lies in the precise and comprehensive determination of how assets adapt to the new management of complex systems, a direct consequence of digitization. As our infrastructure and systems become increasingly digital, it is imperative that the way we manage and maintain our assets evolves accordingly. However, this transition is not always clear or efficient. The existing gap in understanding and implementing asset digitization directly impacts the organization of information associated with these assets. Digital assets are much more than mere pieces of machinery; they represent crucial components in an interconnected digital ecosystem. The lack of a precise understanding of how these assets integrate and behave in this new digital environment compromises our decision-making and management capabilities. This deficiency can lead to operational inefficiencies, unnecessary costs, and ultimately, a decrease in the quality of service and infrastructure reliability.

This article focuses on addressing this challenge from a perspective centered on asset digitization. It provides a detailed practical case of how we can progress in this space through the integration of various models. This comprehensive approach includes interpreting how we define and categorize assets according to established standards, evaluating the criticality of these assets, and combining monitoring models with the Asset Health Index (AHI) model. The integration of these models offers a complete view of asset digitization, covering different levels of complex asset system management, and facilitates a better connection between real-time monitoring and a deeper, long-term understanding of asset condition and performance. The resulting synergy enhances the effectiveness of asset digitization strategies, especially in critical applications such as infrastructure management. A concrete example is presented in the article: the digitization of a set of pumps. This demonstrates how these practices can have a positive impact on asset management and maintenance in the context of digital transformation, contributing to improving the safety, efficiency, and reliability the assets.

Keywords: Asset digitalization, Digital Maintenance, Asset Health Indexing.

1. Introduction

In today's digitization processes, data alone is not enough. The situation is much more complex and requires a strategic and global vision of how to deal with asset modelling. Efficient digitization and asset management pose a complex challenge that demands a multidisciplinary approach from conceptualization to implementation. The term "asset digitization" encompasses designing data representing the asset and the transformation of processes to generate new value. This paper refers to the term "asset digitization" as meaning the aggregate of the terms "digitization", "digitalization" and "digital transformation" of assets. That is, the concept includes everything from the asset's data and information model to processes for extending the value and management of the asset and a broader view of digital transformation (Gong and Ribiere, 2020)

(Raza et al, 2023). Digitalization solutions often emerge from a technological standpoint, but a maintenance-focused approach ensures the longevity and reliability of digitized assets, aligning with business objectives. A visual reference tool is proposed for integrating the Input-Process-Output framework with maintenance processes (Crespo, 2022), aligning with ISO 14224:2016.

Standardization is crucial for the recognizability, interchangeability, and efficient operability of digital assets. Reference architectures, particularly RAMI 4.0 and IIRA, are emphasized for their impact and acceptance in academia and industry. Despite nuanced differences, both architectures employ layers for modularity, flexibility, and incremental updates. This paper aims to introduce a model-based approach to asset digitization in the service of maintenance and asset management, which allows optimizing strategic decisions in the short, medium and long term, in order to improve asset management and maintenance.

2. Methodology

This paper presents a methodology that establishes in a simple and orderly manner the steps for the digitization of assets. Figure 1 outlines the steps to achieve the defined level of digitization. It begins with defining the asset's data model, identifying the physical asset to analyze (serial number and properties), its type based on nature/technology, technical location (position and operational context), and a reference system for geolocation (coordinate system). Subsequently, a model is established to hierarchize and calculate the criticality of assets. Criticality determines the level of digitization, with higher levels for assets of high criticality and lower levels for those of low criticality.

Figure 1 - Models for defining asset digitalization

Monitoring and predictive analytical techniques are justified for highly critical assets, as applying them to non-critical assets could increase system complexity without significant improvements in asset performance. Therefore, for highly critical assets, the next step involves establishing a monitoring model through a network of nodes and sensors that capture information about the asset's condition, operation, and maintenance, developing specific solutions for each. This enables linking data derived from the physical world.

Finally, models for intelligent asset management are defined, tailored to the specific management of each asset. These models structure data by considering human reasoning and

transferring expert knowledge to the model. They are integrated into intelligent platforms for asset management (IAMP App). Different types of models can be established, such as root cause analysis (RCA), reliability-centered maintenance (RCM), condition-based maintenance (CBM), among others. In this document, the Asset Health Index (AHI) is selected as the model. The interpretation of AHI facilitates decision-making in the short, medium, and long term, either for a specific asset or by comparing it with other assets in the infrastructure.

For the application of the proposed methodology, the steps developed for a real-use case are followed, focusing on a power generation plant with a capacity of over 2,000 MW, where the analysis is conducted on the four pumps of a motor pump group.

2.1. Asset Definition Model

The proper handling of entities included in the first step of Figure 1 allows organizing and providing a comprehensive view of the data we have for the asset. These data are then used in various models, such as calculations and simulations, to control the asset according to system requirements. Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between entities, outlining the steps to define the basic data model.

Figure 2 - Sample of asset data model relationship.

In the specific case, the first step involves identifying the physical assets to analyze — here, the four pumps in Unit "A" at the power generation plant: SN-XXX01, SN-XXX02, SN-XXX03, and SN-XXX04. Given the plant's diverse asset types, a list of classes and subclasses is defined to effectively manage maintenance. The pumps belong to the "pump" class and "centrifugal pump" subclass, enabling the distinction of failures and assignment of maintenance plans. Each pump is installed in a physical or functional location, determining its operational context. The tree of functional locations represents the plant's functional structure. Each asset can change functional location throughout its lifespan, facing different operational contexts. The natural linkage of data to technical location and the asset is emphasized. The reference system, essential for effective analysis and maintenance, describes technical locations and plays a crucial role in integrating information systems (geolocation tools like GIS systems). However, it is not considered in this specific case of individual assets in a particular installation.

2.2. Asset Criticality Model

An asset criticality model is essential in infrastructure management, allowing prioritization of assets from high to low importance within the organization. After determining criticality, the framework integrates with other models, such as preventive maintenance plans, monitoring, optimal resource allocation in maintenance, and health models to assess conditions and life

cycle costs. To achieve this, it is crucial to evaluate the criticality of each asset in its technical location within the facility. The risk index or criticality is calculated as the product of the frequency or probability of failure and the consequence of functional failure, considering the sum of severity factors that quantify the impact of failure on the business (Crespo et al., 2016). In Figure 3, the location on the criticality matrix of the pumps in Unit 1 at the power generation plant is visualized. Two pumps with low criticality, three with medium criticality, and four with high criticality are identified. In this use case, the four pumps with high criticality are selected, as digitization is prioritized for critical assets, avoiding the complete process for low-impact economic assets.

Figure 3 - Sample of some pumps on criticality matrix

2.3. Asset Monitoring Model

The development of an asset monitoring model is a complex process involving signal integration and the establishment of a comprehensive Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) process, facilitating the conversion of signals into valuable information related to assets. To establish the monitoring model, it is necessary to define which data to capture for asset management and how to obtain it using monitoring elements and sensors. With identified and installed sensors, an Internet of Things (IoT) monitoring network is configured to relate the physical asset to nodes and sensors for capturing necessary information. In the case study, each pump is equipped with over 50 sensors recording specific and environmental variables. Each variable is stored in an independent database. The IoT network consolidates these information sources into a single database after data mining to ensure data quality. RapidMiner software is employed to extract, chronologically organize, store, and process the information. To obtain a coherent and representative model for each equipment, non-equivalent variables capturing equipment aging are selected. Out of over 50 available variables, 80% are discarded using a correlation criterion, considering only 10 representative variables for the health index model.

2.4. Asset Health Model

The health model is based on the methodology precisely developed by Serra J. et al (2019) and Crespo A. (2022). This paper does not provide a detailed description of the mathematical model for calculating the health index but aims to present an intelligent management model that completes the digitization process of the analyzed asset. Figure 4 outlines the proposed asset health model using the six steps methodology as elaborated in [39]. The complete model integration with the platform involves data extraction, processing, and loading (ETL Processes), providing necessary inputs for databases (DB Processes) needed for calculating the asset health index interpreting their impact on the asset's health through normalized and pondered modifiers (asset class, normal life, location and load factors, age, maintenance and other incidents files,

sensors etc.). The direct interpretation of the Asset Health Index (AHI) for an individual asset, or a comparison across a set of assets, facilitates decision-making at the specific asset level and helps establish maintenance strategies.

Figure 4 - The AHI model presentation using the DMM framework (Crespo, 2022).

3. Results and Discussions

The definition of the asset with its criticality, monitoring, and asset health index leads to a complete digitization process of the analyzed asset. As the output of the entire process, all the necessary information for the management and maintenance of the asset is integrated and made available. In Figure 5, the result of applying the health model is shown, represented in a BI App, which facilitates the user in defining the strategy and decision-making, all of which are outcomes of applying the complete digitization process. Figure 5 illustrates the evolution of the health index for each pump and the relative comparison of each, depicting the health status and relative deterioration (represented by the pump diameter) over the operational time of each pump. It is observed that pumps U1-MBA-BFP-1 and U1-MBB-BFP-1 have accumulated the highest number of operating hours and are in the worst health condition. However, pump U1-MBA-BFP-2, despite accumulating more operating hours, has better health than pump U1-MBB-BFP-2, which has a greater than expected deterioration.

Figure 5 - Control panel from AHI results

4. Conclusions

The comprehensive asset digitalization process proposed stands out for its strategic approach and effective application in a real-use case. It facilitates efficient asset management, optimizing resources, and enhancing decision-making. The execution of the steps outlined in Figure 1 allows for the systematic organization of the asset digitalization process, ensuring that all information, data, methodologies, and processes contribute the necessary value for proper asset management and maintenance. By mediating the relationships among different involved models,

the paper successfully achieves the intended digitalization goal, overseeing all entities participating in the management and maintenance process.

This strategic approach to digitization not only streamlines asset-related operations but also establishes a framework that maximizes the utility of available resources. The integration of various models ensures a holistic understanding of the asset landscape, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions. Moreover, the process promotes transparency and control by overseeing all entities involved, contributing to a seamless and well-coordinated management and maintenance workflow.

Acknowledgements

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References

Cañas, H., Mula, J., Campuzano-Bolarín, F., and Poler, R. (2022). *A conceptual framework for smart production planning and control in Industry 4.0*. doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2022.108659.

Crespo Márquez, A. (2022). *Springer Series in Reliability Engineering. Digital Maintenance Management Guiding Digital Transformation in Maintenance*.

Crespo Márquez, A., Moreu De León, P., Sola Rosique, A., & Gómez Fernández, J. F. (2016). *Criticality Analysis for Maintenance Purposes: A Study for Complex In-service Engineering Assets*. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, 32(2), 519–533. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.1769>

De La Fuente, A., González-Prida, V., Crespo, A., Gómez, J. and Guillén, A. (2018). *Advanced Techniques for Assets Maintenance Management*. pp. 51–62, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.08.260.

Gong, C. and Ribiere, V. (2020). *Developing a unified definition of digital transformation*. doi: 10.1016/j.technovation.2020.102217.

Guillén, A. J., Crespo, A., Gómez, J. and Sanz, M. D. (2016). *A framework for effective management of condition based maintenance programs in the context of industrial development of E-Maintenance strategies*. doi: 10.1016/j.compind.2016.07.003

Guillén, A. J., Crespo, A., Macchi, M. and Gómez, J. (2016). *On the role of Prognostics and Health Management in advanced maintenance systems*. *Production Planning & Control*, vol. 27, no. 12, pp. 991–1004, doi: 10.1080/09537287.2016.1171920.

Lee, J., Bagheri, B. and Kao, H.-A. (2015). *A Cyber-Physical Systems architecture for Industry 4.0-based manufacturing systems*. doi: 10.1016/j.mfglet.2014.12.001.

Raza, Z., Woxenius, J., Altuntas Vural, C. and Lind, M. (2023). *Digital transformation of maritime logistics: Exploring trends in the liner shipping segment*. *Comput Ind*, vol. 145, p. 103811, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compind.2022.103811.

Serra, J., Crespo, A. and Gómez, J. (2019). *Analysis of the impact of the Asset Health Index in a Maintenance Strategy*.

3rd OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 10.00	WELCOME - OPENING ADRESSES			
10.00 10.45	PLENARY SESSION ISABEL PARDO DE VERA. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE: PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO			
10.45 11.15	COFFEE BREAK			
11.15 12.45	RAIL SESSION Digitalization in manufacturing and O&M of railway rolling stock	CIBERSECURITY SESSION Decentralized cybersecurity of critical engineering assets	Strategy & Planning	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 1
12.45 14.15	LUNCH			
14.15 15.00	PLENARY SESSION CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH, COPPERLEAF. OPTIMISED ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING WITH COPPERLEAF - MAKING THE RIGHT DECISIONS AT THE RIGHT TIME TO MAXIMISE VALUE AND MEET STRATEGIC GOALS			
15.00 16.30	RAIL SESSION Digital Transformation in Rail Infrastructure	DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT SESSION Digitalization and Risk Management of Critical Engineering Assets	Life Cycle Management 1	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 2
16.30 17.00	COFFEE BREAK			
17.00 18.30	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	HYDROGEN SESSION Technical and Energetic Challenges in the Transition from Natural gas to Hydrogen	Life Cycle Management 2	SPECIAL SESSION Digital IAMS for integral LCM
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL			

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09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION ABEL GOMES. APPLUS. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE LA INFRAESTRUCTURA			
09.45 10.30	PLENARY SESSION NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUAEPAL.			
10.30 11.00	COFFEE BREAK			
11.00 12.30	APMI-AEM SESSION Maintenance and Asset Management. Future and Trends in the Iberian Region	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION BIOCHAR Applications and Circular Economy	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 1	WORKSHOP The Copperleaf optimization game
12.30 14.00	LUNCH			
14.00 14.45	PLENARY SESSION. TIAGO FERNANDES, ALFONSO LACERDA. EVORA GOLD PARTNER SAP. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE- THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL WORLD.			
14.45 16.15	APMI-AEM SESSION People in Maintenance and Asset management in the Iberian Region	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Improving asset management in local governments	Management Systems and Standards 1	Sustainability 1
16.15 16.45	COFFEE BREAK			
16.45 18.15	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Building sustainable communities with asset management	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 2	Management Systems and Standards 2
20.00	GALA DINNER			

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09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION. JOE AMADI-ECHENDU , DAVID MCKEON,, EDMEA ADELL, ALAN WILSON. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS .			
09.45 11.15	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION The role of asset management in the resilience of critical infrastructure	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION	Sustainability 2	Risk & Reliability
11.15 11.45	COFFEE BREAK			
11.45 13.15	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION Intelligent Asset Management : People, Processes and Technology as enablers for ISO 55001 Certification	Data Asset and Digital Transformation	Sustainability 3	People & Competence
13.15 14.00	CLOSING CEREMONY			
14.00	LUNCH			

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10.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 44. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO. ISABEL PARDO DE VERA.
10.45	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY CAF
11.15 AUDITORIUM I	RAIL SESSION. ID 119. DIGITALIZATION IN MANUFACTURING AND O&M OF RAILWAY ROLLING STOCK.
	<i>Chair: Luis Andrade Ferreira. Centro de Competências Ferroviário Javier de la Cruz, CAF José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Alexandra Prates. CP Metropolitano de Lisboa</i>
11.15 AUDITORIUM III	CYBERSECURITY SESSION. ID 58. NAORIS PROTOCOL: WORLD'S FIRST DECENTRALIZED CYBERSECURITY MESH ARCHITECTURE. DAVID CARVALHO
	ID 116. BRIDGING THE GAP: WEB 3.0 AND CYBER-PHYSICAL INTEGRATION IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT
	<i>Chair: João Santos. Naoris David Carvalho. Naoris Miguel Oliveira. University of Aveiro Luis Ramalhais Santos. OET Jorge Liça. OE Carlos Ribeiro. Ex Director CSI</i>
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ID 28	ASSET MANAGEMENT: QUAL O VOLUME DE DADOS É NECESSARIO PARA A TOMADA DE DECISÃO DE ALTO VALOR AGREGADO?. CELSO DE AZEVEDO
ID 38	COMO MELHORAR O PLANO DE INVESTIMENTOS DE UMA ORGANIZAÇÃO DE CAPITAL INTENSIVO. MARIANA CASALTA

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ID 111	FROM DATA TO DECISIONS: EMPOWERING PIPELINE OPERATORS WITH ACTIONABLE INSIGHTS. ANA SILVA
11.15 ROOM 5	PERFORMANCE AND CONDITION OF PHYSICAL ASSETS. SESSION 1. CHAIR ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO
ID 9	PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT IN RETAIL WATER UTILITIES: GUIDING ASSET MANAGEMENT BY IDENTIFYING PEERS AND TARGETS. HERMILIO VILARINHO
ID 12	ASSESSMENT OF THE TECHNICAL AND FUNCTIONAL PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC BUILDINGS. FILIPA SALVADO
ID 18	TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF ALTERNATIVE REFRIGERANTS WITH LOWER GWP FOR THE RETROFIT OF HEAT PUMPS WITH R410A. PEDRO BARANDIER
ID 48	ENERGETIC AND ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE HVAC TEMPERATURE SETPOINT ADJUSTMENT IN COMMERCIAL AND SERVICE BUILDINGS. PEDRO BARANDIER
ID 62	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS E A OTIMIZAÇÃO DA EFICIÊNCIA EM LABORATÓRIOS DE ENSAIOS DE MATERIAIS. EDUARDO GANILHO
ID 92	FROM VIDEO ACQUISITION TO EXPERIMENTAL MODAL ANALYSIS. TIAGO SILVA
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15.00 AUDITORIUM I	RAIL SESSION. ID 120. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN RAIL INFRASTRUCTURE.
	<i>Chair: Esther Mateo Rodríguez. ADIF Dolores Sanz. IDOM Fernando Vara. ACCIONA Valentí Fontseré. COMSA Montserrat Álvarez. Ineco Paulo Duarte. PFP Rui Coutinho. Infraestruturas de Portugal</i>

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ID 126	DIGITALIZACIÓN Y GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. BEGOÑA MARTÍN Y JOÃO DIONISIO. COMSA
ID 131	PROJETO TRANSVERSAL DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS PARA O MATERIAL CIRCULANTE E OFICINAS FERROVIÁRIAS - UMA ABORDAGEM PRÁTICA PARA A MELHORIA DOS PROCESSOS E DA PRODUTIVIDADE. SILVIA FERREIRA Y MIGUEL RODRIGUES. CP
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20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL OCEANÁRIO

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09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 123. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE INFRAESTRUCTURAS. ABEL GOMES. APPLUS.
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 134. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUA. NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL.
10.30	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY AYESA
11.00 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 121 MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT: FUTURE AND TRENDS IN THE IBERO-AMERICAN SPACE <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez Claudio Rodríguez. AEM Diogo Brito. APMI Marcela Scalco. ABRAMAN</i>
	ID 122. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Pedro Conceição (SONAE ARAUCO) Hugo Lebre (INFRASPEAK) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM III	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION. ID 95: BIOCHAR APPLICATIONS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY. ATIV <i>Chair: Cátia Neves. ATIV - Mota ENGIL</i>
11.00 ROOM 2	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 1. ANTONIO GUILLÉN LÓPEZ.
ID 11	THE IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE ASSET MAINTENANCE IN TELECOMS DOMAIN IN EMERGING MARKETS. CHARLES OKEYIA
ID 13	CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY AND OVERCOMING THE DIGITALIZATION DEFICIT OF THE AECO INDUSTRY. SEYED REZVAN
ID 89	IMPLANTAÇÃO DE SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA EMBASA: INTEGRAÇÃO DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO. RINALDO CAMURUGY
ID 33	MODELAÇÃO PARAMÉTRICA DE ANOMALIAS EM TÚNEIS FERROVIÁRIOS. ANA ROCHA
ID 106	A VALUE-BASED DECISION-MAKING PROCESS FOR DIGITAL TWINNING OPPORTUNITIES IN RAIL AND ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET MANAGEMENT. JOÃO VIEIRA

ID 3	DIGITALIZATION STRATEGY FOR ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY'S NET-ZERO TRANSITION. <i>ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM II	WORKSHOP. ID 5. THE COPPERLEAF OPTIMIZATION GAME. CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH.
12.30	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
14.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 130. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE – THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN A DIGITAL WORLD. TIAGO FERNANDES, SAP & ALFONSO LACERDA, EVORA.
14.45 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 124. PEOPLE IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION .
	<i>Chair: Daniel Gaspar José Luis Bernal. MASA Álvaro Rodríguez Prieto. UNED Paulo Peixoto (ATEC) Mário Aguiam (ISQ)</i>
14.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 96. IMPROVING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
14.45 ROOM 2	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 1. CHAIR RITA BRITO.
ID 19	SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA MANUTENÇÃO DE PAVIMENTOS RODOVIÁRIOS. <i>JOSÉ VAZ</i>
ID 27	LOS SISTEMAS DE GETIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE CARRETERAS COMO HERRAMIENTAS PARA LA OPTIMIZACIÓN DE LOS PRESUPUESTOS DE CONSERVACIÓN. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 83	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS APLICADA EMPRESAS DE SANEAMENTO: IMPLANTAÇÃO DE MODELO NA EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO (EMBASA). <i>ALISSON BRANDÃO</i>
ID 77	NEW VALUE PERSPECTIVE FOR SOCIAL PRICELESS ASSETS THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS. <i>JOAQUÍN ORDIERES-MERÉ</i>
ID 78	DESAFIOS ATUAIS DA E-REDES NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS TÉCNICOS. <i>MIGUEL FREITAS</i>
14.45 ROOM 5	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 1. CHAIR: ANA SILVA.
ID 56	AVALIAÇÃO EX-ANTE DA PRODUÇÃO DE MISTURAS BETUMINOSAS CONSIDERANDO TRÊS CENÁRIOS DE PRODUÇÃO ALTERNATIVOS. <i>ANA ROCHA</i>

ID 71	THE SYNERGY BETWEEN LEAN PHILOSOPHY AND VALUE ENGINEERING FOR NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 72	SOLUÇÃO CONJUGADA DE CONSTRUÇÃO TRADICIONAL E TECNOLOGIA MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS SUSTENTÁVEIS EM CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTES</i>
ID 75	"BOTICAR" PROJECT – THE FIRST STEPS TOWARDS DECARBONISATION IN PORTUGAL
ID 90	IMPLANTAÇÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NO SISTEMA DE ABASTECIMENTO DE ÁGUA E ESGOTAMENTO SANITÁRIO DE BARRA DE POJUCA NA EMBASA – EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO. <i>RINALDO CAMURUGY</i>
16.15	COFFEE BREAK
16.45 AUDITORIUM I	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR JOAQUÍN ORDIERES
	GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. TALGO
ID 128	IMPORTANCIA DEL FACTOR HUMANO EN LA APLICACIÓN DE LA INGENIERÍA DEL MANTENIMIENTO EN LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS. <i>JOSÉ LUIS BERNAL. MASA</i>
ID 115	UN ENFOQUE UNIFICADO DE LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS MEDIANTE SAP Y BIM EN AT/MT/BT ELÉCTRICA. <i>IGNACIO MORATALLA AGUIRRE. AYESA</i>
16.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 97. BUILDING SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITIES WITH ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
16.45 ROOM 2	DATA ASSETS & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 2. CHAIR: VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA.
ID 15	INDUSTRIAL IOT AND 3D DIGITAL TWIN FOR REAL TIME-EVERGREENING OF ENGINEERING ASSETS SUBJECTED TO CORROSION UNDER INSULATION. <i>ALVARO RODRÍGUEZ-PRIETO</i>
ID 26	UNA EFICAZ GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE REDES DE CARRETERAS A PARTIR DE GEMELOS DIGITALES. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 70	OVERVIEW OF THE USE OF DATA ASSETS IN THE CONTEXT OF PORTUGUESE COMPANIES: COMPARISON BETWEEN SMES AND LARGE COMPANIES. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 73	MODIFICAÇÃO DO MÉTODO DELPHI PARA APLICAÇÃO NUM QUESTIONÁRIO SOBRE A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>SAMUEL MESSIAS</i>
ID 103	NDE & SENSING SOLUTIONS FOR PIPELINE STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING. <i>GABRIEL DINIS</i>
ID 112	DIGITALIZING BUILDING MAINTENANCE: BIM-POWERED ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS. <i>ANA SILVA</i>

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16.45 ROOM 5	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 2. FILIPA SALVADO.
ID 16	COLLECTIVE USE BUILDINGS ASSET MANAGEMENT BASED ON TECHNICAL AND ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO</i>
ID 35	IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS OF AN ISO 55001 CERTIFIED ASSET MANAGEMENT MODEL IN THE NATURAL GAS INDUSTRY. <i>JAVIER SERRA</i>
ID 41	IMPLEMENTACIÓN DE UN PLAN DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS SEGÚN LA NORMA ISO 55001 EN LA CENTRAL DE GENERACIÓN ELÉCTRICA COLMITO.
ID 63	A EVOLUÇÃO E PERSPETIVAS DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS: UM MODELO ABRANGENTE E INTEGRADO DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS. <i>JOAQUIM CABRAL MARTINS</i>
ID 82	CERTIFICAÇÃO ISO 55001 NA E-REDES – UMA AVALIAÇÃO APÓS DOIS ANOS. <i>CRISTINA CARVALHO</i>
ID 110	IMPORTÂNCIA DO ALINHAMENTO DAS FUNÇÕES ORGANIZACIONAIS E DA ESTRUTURAÇÃO DOS ATIVOS NA TOMADA DE DECISÃO SOBRE INVESTIMENTOS NO SETOR DA ÁGUA. <i>JAIME GABRIEL SILVA</i>
20.00	GALA DINNER KAIS RESTAURANTE

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09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION ID 113. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS.
	Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez David Mckewon. Vicepresidente honorario del Instituto de Gestión de Activos Joe Amadi Echendu. Presidente de la Junta Directiva de la Sociedad Internacional de Gestión de Activos de Ingeniería Edmea Adell. Presidente de IFRAMI y miembro de ISO/TC 251 Asset Management Alan Wilson. Representante del Comité de Gestión de Activos de la Federación Europea de Sociedades Nacionales de Mantenimiento
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION. ID 135. THE ROLE OF ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE RESILIENCE OF CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE. EPAL
	Chair: Ana Margarida Luís. AdP Valor Miguel Freitas. E-REDES Vanessa Martins. EPAL Javier Serra. ENAGÁS Infraestructuras de Portugal
09.45 AUDITORIUM III	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION. CHAIR EDUARDO LEITE
ID 8	EUROPEAN ACTION TOWARDS MORE ENTREPRENEURIAL AND INNOVATIVE UNIVERSITIES. <i>NUNO ALMEIDA</i>
ID 74	ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: FAILURE PREVENTION AS A PILLAR FOR SUCESS. <i>EDUARDO LEITE</i>
ID 20	NETOBRA. A TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT FOR URBAN RESILIENCE IN THE AECO SECTOR. <i>SEYED REZVANI</i>
ID 117	SPOTLITE. RISK MONITORING FROM SPACE. <i>NUNO DURO</i>
ID 127	DIPROTOS. SISTEMA DE MONITORIZAÇÃO E VIGILÂNCIA DOS ATIVOS: PARQUES PÚBLICOS INFANTIS E DE LAZER. <i>ANTÓNIO ROQUE</i>
ID 94	BCIRCLE. PROJECTO "BOTICHAR". UMA UNIDADE DE PRODUÇÃO EFICIENTE E ESCALÁVEL. <i>DIEGO ARÁN</i>
ID 102	AECYCLE. SUSTAINABLE AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 109	CASADOMO. HABITAÇÃO INOVADORA E SUSTENTÁVEL EM SUPERDOBE MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS DA CIDADE DA PRAIA - CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTÉS</i>
09.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 2. CHAIR ANA LUÍSA CABRITA
ID 114	SUSTAINABILITY AND OTHER OUTCOMES - THE VALUE OF A STRATEGIC ASSET MANAGEMENT APPROACH. <i>DAVID MCKEOWN</i>

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ID 31	A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN EUROPE TO MEASURE THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT POLICIES, INDUSTRY ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY. <i>KHULOUD KALTHOUM</i>
ID 17	PROTECTING AND REALIZING VALUE FROM POLLINATION ASSETS: BEEKEEPING OR ASSET MANAGEMENT APPLIED TO NATURAL ASSETS?. <i>AZUCENA MARQUES</i>
ID 52	CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN INDUSTRY 5.0 – A RESEARCH AGENDA
ID 54	A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION AND AWARENESS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES BY MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN SANGO-OTA REGION, OGUN STATE NIGERIA. <i>ISRAEL DUNMADE</i>
ID 107	HARNESSING THE POWER OF BIOMIMICRY FOR SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION IN PRODUCT DESIGN AND INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT. <i>ARUNA M</i>
09.45 ROOM 5	RISK & RELIABILITY. CHAIR ANTONIO SÁNCHEZ.
ID 6	DATA MODEL TO DIGITIZATION OF CRITICALITY ANALYSIS IN RAILWAY SYSTEMS. <i>ÁNGEL MENA</i>
ID 1	APLICACIÓN DEL MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO (MGM) ALINEADO A UN PROCESO INTEGRAL DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS.CASO DE ESTUDIO: SINEA PERÚ, EMPRESA LÍDER EN LATINOAMÉRICA DEL SECTOR DE PRODUCCIÓN ENVASES RECICLADOS PARA BEBIDAS COMERCIALES (PET). <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 7	MATRIZ DE CRITICIDAD CUALITATIVA DE RIESGO (MCCR) APLICADA EN UNA LÍNEA DE PRODUCCIÓN DE ENVASES BIODEGRADABLES, <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 30	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VISÃO GERAL DA ESTRUTURA E FUNCIONAMENTO. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
ID 25	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VALIDAÇÃO COM BASE EM DADOS REAIS. <i>JOÃO VINAGRE AMADO</i>
11.15	COFFEE BREAK
11.45 AUDITORIUM I	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION. ID 125. INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT : PEOPLE , PROCESSES AND TECHNOLOGY AS ENABLERS FOR ISO 55001 CERTIFICATION. EVORA/SAP
	<i>Chair: Patrícia Franganito (Bureau Veritas) Tiago Fernandes (SAP EMEA) João Moura (Ernst & Young) Paula Branco (Metro do Porto) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>

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11.45 AUDITORIUM III	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 3. CHAIR HUGO PATRÍCIO.
ID 37	GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIER-BASED APPROACH ON WASTEWATER NETWORK AGE PREDICTION FOR CRITICAL ASSETS IDENTIFICATION. <i>RICARDO FERREIRA</i>
ID 49	DIGITALIZAÇÃO E ANÁLISE FUNCIONAL INTEGRADA (AFI) NO PROCESSO DE TOMADA DE DECISÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>HUGO BRANQUINHO</i>
ID 50	INFODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE DETECTION OF BRIDGES. <i>JORGE ALEXANDRE VIEIRA</i>
ID 57	MONITOREO DE LA SALUD ESTRUCTURAL MEDIANTE REALIDAD AUMENTADA Y VIRTUAL: UNA REVISIÓN INTEGRAL. <i>MATÍAS VALENZUELA</i>
ID 66	AVALIAÇÃO METODOLÓGICA DA APLICABILIDADE DA MONITORIZAÇÃO POR SATÉLITE NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS RODOFERROVIÁRIOS. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
11.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 3. CHAIR JOSÉ CAMPOS E MATOS.
ID 32	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS DE ÁGUAS PLUVIAIS EM MEIO URBANO EM PORTUGAL – DESAFIOS PARA O SETOR. <i>RITA SALGADO BRITO</i>
ID 39	REALITY CAPTURE AND MODELLING FOR DIGITAL WATER MANAGEMENT: CASE STUDY OF WATER INFRASTRUCTURE ASSETS IN BRAZIL. <i>WAGNER CARVALHO</i>
ID 81	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA AVALIAÇÃO DA QUALIDADE NA GESTÃO E OTIMIZAÇÃO DE ATIVOS FOTOVOLTAICOS. <i>TERESA CANELAS</i>
ID 93	PATHWAYS TOWARDS NET-ZERO: MARKET DATA INSIGHTS ON PORTUGUESE REAL ESTATE ENERGY PERFORMANCE
ID 100	TRANSIÇÃO DIGITAL E INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA NO SETOR AECO - ESTRATÉGIAS INTEGRADAS PARA UM FUTURO SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 105	COMO TORNAR UM AMS – ASSET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OPERACIONAL E SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>EDMEA ADELL</i>
11.45 ROOM 5	PEOPLE AND COMPETENCE. CHAIR TICO MONTEIRO
ID 10	INNOVATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT SKILLS TOWARDS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO SILVA</i>
ID 53	PROFICIÊNCIA DIGITAL DE ESTUDANTES DE ENGENHARIA: DESAFIOS E OPORTUNIDADES NO CENÁRIO EUROPEU. <i>CELIA DO CARMO LEANDRO</i>

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ID 60	FORTALECENDO A RESILIÊNCIA CLIMÁTICA EM SÃO TOMÉ E PRÍNCIPE: CAPACITAÇÃO DE JORNALISTAS PARA UMA COMUNICAÇÃO EFICAZ.
ID 87	PROPUESTA DE METODOLOGÍA DE GESTIÓN DEL CAMBIO COMO COMPLEMENTO AL MARCO DE REFERENCIA PARA UNA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS INTANGIBLES Y CONOCIMIENTO. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA
ID 118	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA FORMAÇÃO PARA UM MELHOR DESEMPENHO NOS MÉTODOS E PLANEAMENTO DA MANUTENÇÃO DE ATIVOS. DÉRCIO DIAS
ID 2	CRITICAL ASSETS AND VALUE NETWORKS IN RESILIENT INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN THE EU OUTERMOST REGIONS. EDUARDO LEITE
13.15 AUDITORIUM I	CLOSING CEREMONY BEST PAPER DIGITALIZATION BEST PAPER SUSTAINABILITY ENTERPREUNERSHIP COMPETITION LIFETIME ACHIEVEMENT AWARD
13.45	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
